

Consistency of Manual Sense Annotation and Integration into the TüBa-D/Z Treebank

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Abstract

Since sense-annotated corpora serve as gold standards for the development, training, and evaluation of word sense disambiguation (WSD) systems, their availability is a necessary prerequisite for WSD. The purpose of the present paper is to describe the manual annotation of a selected set of lemmas in the TüBa-D/Z treebank [9, 21] with senses from the German wordnet GermaNet [7, 8]. With the sense annotation for a selected set of 109 words (30 nouns and 79 verbs) occurring together 17 910 times in the TüBa-D/Z, the treebank currently represents the largest manually sense-annotated corpus available for GermaNet.

This paper describes the annotation process, presents statistics, analyzes inter-annotator agreement (and disagreement), and documents the technical integration of the sense annotations into the most recent release 9.1 of the TüBa-D/Z. The publication of this paper is accompanied by making the described sense annotations available to the research community.

1 Introduction and Motivation

The purpose of this paper is to describe the manual sense-annotation of a selected set of lemmas in the TüBa-D/Z treebank [9, 21] with special focus on inter-annotator agreement and technical integration into the TüBa-D/Z.¹ The sense inventory used for tagging word senses is taken from GermaNet [7, 8]. The underlying textual resource, the TüBa-D/Z treebank, is a German newspaper corpus already semi-automatically enriched with high-quality annotations at various levels of language including parts of speech, morphology, syntactic constituency, etc. The use of treebank data is motivated by at least two considerations: (i) the grammatical information contained in a treebank makes it possible to utilize deep syntactic and

¹The present paper substantially extends the research described earlier in [9]: it presents updated statistics on the sense annotation, reports frequency, polysemy, and inter-annotator agreement for each lemma, and documents the technical integration into the treebank.

semantic information for word sense disambiguation [6, 3]; (ii) since the TüBa-D/Z is based on newspaper text, this ensures a broad coverage of topical materials such as politics, economy, society, environmental issues, sports, arts and entertainment.

This paper starts with a brief overview of the resources TüBa-D/Z and GermaNet (Section 2) and with statistics on the sense annotations, including frequency, polysemy, and inter-annotator agreement for each lemma (Section 3). Sections 4 and 5 describe the annotation process and analyze inter-annotator agreement (and disagreement) for the annotated lemmas. The technical integration of the sense annotations into the most recent release of the TüBa-D/Z is documented in Section 6. Finally, Section 7 concludes with a comparison to related work and an outlook to future work.

The publication of this paper is accompanied by making the described sense annotations available to the research community. Therefore, the sense annotations have been integrated into release 9.1 of the TüBa-D/Z (as of December 2014).

2 Resources

The Underlying Textual Resource for the sense-tagged corpus presented here is the syntactically annotated Tübingen Treebank of Written German (TüBa-D/Z) [21], the largest manually annotated treebank for German. It includes the following annotation layers: part-of-speech, inflectional morphology, lemmatization, syntactic constituency, grammatical functions, named entity classification, anaphora and coreference relations. The textual material for the treebank is taken from the daily newspaper “die tageszeitung” (taz). The current release 9.1 of the TüBa-D/Z (as of December 2014) contains 1 569 916 tokens occurring in 85 358 sentences that are taken from 3 444 newspaper articles.

The Sense Inventory for the sense-annotation is taken from GermaNet [7, 8], a lexical semantic network that is modeled after the Princeton WordNet for English [5]. It represents semantic concepts as *synsets*, i.e., as sets of (near-)synonymous words (referred to as *lexical units*), that are interlinked by semantic relations. GermaNet covers the three word categories of adjectives, nouns, and verbs, each of which is hierarchically structured in terms of the hypernymy relation of synsets. GermaNet’s version 9.0 (release of April 2014) contains 121 810 lexical units, which are grouped into 93 246 synsets. Using a wordnet as the gold standard for the sense inventory is fully in line with standard practice for English where the Princeton WordNet is typically taken.

3 Sense-Annotated Lemmas

The sense annotation in the TüBa-D/Z is geared toward the lexical sample task in word sense disambiguation (as in many existing corpora [2, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19]), rather than toward the all-words task. The decision for sense annotation of a lexical sample is motivated by the requirements of machine learning. Sense-annotated

data are useful for training (semi-)automatic machine learning models only if there are sufficiently many instances for each item to be classified. Due to limitations of how much text can reasonably be annotated manually in an all-words, sense-annotated corpus, the resulting numbers of instances for each token are only of sufficient frequency for machine-learning applications if manual sense annotation concentrates on a lexical sample.

A total of 109 lemmas (30 nouns and 79 verbs) were selected for manual sense annotation. These lemmas have two or more senses in GermaNet and occur at least 21 times in the TüBa-D/Z – to ensure a reasonable lower bound of data instances for machine learning purposes. The average frequency for an annotated lemma is 164. Altogether, 17 910 occurrences of the 109 lemmas are sense annotated in the TüBa-D/Z 9.0.²

The 30 annotated nouns occur 8 803 times in the treebank – at least 24 times and at most 1 699 times. On average, there are 293 annotated occurrences per noun lemma. The average polysemy (number of senses in GermaNet) is 4.1 for the annotated nouns, ranging from 2-7 senses. Table 3 lists the nouns in decreasing order of their number of occurrences in the treebank (column *Freq.*). Column *GN* contains the noun’s number of senses in GermaNet, while column *#s* lists the numbers of senses for which at least one annotation exists in the treebank. A superscript + indicates the existence of at least one token for which no GermaNet sense is annotated. These cases occur, for example, for idiomatic expressions or figurative meanings where it is not obvious from the context which sense to chose. Inter-annotator agreement (columns *IAA* and *K*) of the manual sense annotation will be discussed in Section 5 below.

Nouns	Freq.	GN	#s	IAA	K	Nouns	Freq.	GN	#s	IAA	K
Frau	1699	3	3	98.7	96.0	Anschlag	99	5	3 ⁺	95.9	61.4
Mann	1114	3	3	98.8	94.7	Spur	94	5	5 ⁺	84.7	73.1
Land	1112	7	7 ⁺	97.9	95.5	Bein	91	3	1 ⁺	97.4	-1.3
Partei	811	3	3	97.3	62.6	Runde	83	6	6	92.0	88.1
Haus	789	5	5	85.8	60.7	Karte	76	4	4	99.6	100.0
Grund	460	5	5	99.8	96.9	Sender	76	5	4	83.8	60.8
Stunde	426	4	4	98.1	92.8	Stuhl	60	3	3	98.0	100.0
Stimme	289	4	4	98.0	96.0	Ausschuß	50	2	1	100.0	NaN
Mal	284	2	1	100.0	NaN	Bestimmung	48	6	4	90.8	79.2
Kopf	269	6	4 ⁺	97.8	84.0	Gewinn	48	3	3	95.7	89.2
Band	159	6	5	98.7	96.9	Überraschung	42	3	3	96.6	93.0
Tor	137	4	4	100.0	100.0	Teilnahme	37	3	1	98.9	NaN
Fuß	129	3	3	99.1	79.7	Kette	25	4	4	73.9	62.5
Höhe	126	4	4	65.8	11.3	Abfall	24	4	2	100.0	100.0
Freundin	122	3	2	97.1	95.9	Abgabe	24	5	3	100.0	100.0

Table 1: 30 sense-annotated nouns.

²All statistics reported in the present paper are taken from the most recent versions of the TüBa-D/Z (release 9.1) and GermaNet (release 9.0) – with the only exception of inter-annotator agreement figures, which were calculated on the basis of TüBa-D/Z 8.0 and GermaNet 8.0, as the most current versions available at the time the annotation process started.

For verbs, 9 107 occurrences are annotated with the senses of 79 verb lemmas. The average occurrence per verb lemma is 115 with the least frequent verb occurring 21 times, the most frequent one 801 times. The average polysemy is 2.8, with the most polysemous verb showing 14 senses in GermaNet. Table 3 lists the 79 selected lemmas for verbs – again ordered by their frequency in the TüBa-D/Z (column *Freq.*) and with their number of senses in GermaNet (column *GN*), the number of occurring senses (column *#s*), as well as inter-annotator agreement (columns *IAA* and *K*).

Verbs	Freq.	GN	#s	IAA	K	Verbs	Freq.	GN	#s	IAA	K
heißen	801	4	4	94.0	90.9	beschränken	78	2	2	96.7	93.2
gelten	502	5	5	97.7	96.2	betragen	73	2	1	100.0	NaN
setzen	404	14	9+	79.5	75.4	beraten	70	3	3	90.8	81.4
erhalten	399	4	4+	89.2	76.4	merken	62	2	2	98.1	89.9
sitzen	345	7	6+	92.4	85.6	entziehen	61	3	2	96.2	92.6
fragen	344	2	2	99.7	99.0	widmen	60	2	2	100.0	100.0
aussehen	231	2	2	92.1	75.8	empfehlen	58	3	3	100.0	100.0
reden	227	3	3+	80.0	45.8	gestalten	57	2	2	96.3	78.0
sterben	220	2	2	98.4	79.2	bekennen	54	2	2	97.9	95.7
ankündigen	211	2	2	100.0	100.0	wundern	54	2	2	97.8	94.5
unterstützen	188	2	2	95.7	38.1	auffallen	51	2	2	97.8	95.1
bedeuten	187	3	3	98.1	79.2	engagieren	51	2	2	100.0	100.0
verkaufen	186	5	4+	92.5	75.8	raten	46	2	2	100.0	100.0
verurteilen	180	2	2+	96.0	86.6	rücken	45	2	2	100.0	100.0
leisten	176	3	3	90.3	83.1	bedenken	43	3	2	97.6	94.0
bauen	167	3	3+	95.4	83.2	versammeln	42	2	2	97.0	93.9
verschwinden	159	2	2	73.8	47.4	vollziehen	42	2	2	96.9	93.4
gründen	148	4	4	99.2	93.0	erweitern	41	2	2	97.1	84.1
reichen	146	4	4	95.6	91.8	zugehen	41	6	4+	94.3	87.6
geschehen	145	2	2+	98.4	49.5	gestehen	40	2	2	90.0	80.0
herrschen	128	2	2	99.0	90.4	berufen	39	2	2	100.0	100.0
präsentieren	127	2	2	98.9	98.0	klappen	39	3	2	100.0	100.0
informieren	125	2	2	98.2	93.0	kündigen	39	2	2	71.4	42.9
freuen	121	2	2	90.9	64.0	trauen	39	4	4	92.2	91.1
verdienen	115	2	2	100.0	100.0	stehlen	36	2	1+	100.0	100.0
demonstrieren	111	3	3	87.5	77.5	verstoßen	36	2	2	100.0	100.0
holen	110	5	5+	74.2	65.4	zurückgeben	36	2	2	100.0	100.0
aufrufen	105	2	2	99.0	66.3	ärgern	36	2	2	100.0	100.0
verfolgen	105	6	6	91.8	89.0	befassen	35	2	2+	96.9	86.0
weitergehen	101	2	2	98.9	88.3	einschränken	35	2	2	100.0	100.0
besitzen	99	2	2	92.7	84.2	identifizieren	34	3	3	92.6	88.3
versichern	99	3	3	96.5	80.9	beschweren	33	3	2	100.0	100.0
vorliegen	96	2	2	95.0	84.9	vorschreiben	31	2	1	96.2	0.0
enthalten	94	2	2	100.0	100.0	nützen	29	2	2	100.0	NaN
liefern	93	4	4+	88.0	82.5	kleben	28	2	2	87.5	74.3
erweisen	89	3	3	97.2	84.6	verdoppeln	26	2	2	100.0	100.0
existieren	88	2	2	98.6	0.0	fressen	25	3	2	72.7	54.3
drängen	84	3	3	88.2	81.7	wiedergeben	24	3	2	76.2	40.0
behandeln	82	4	4	85.6	78.0	verlesen	21	2	1	100.0	NaN
begrüßen	79	2	2	98.5	96.2						

Table 2: 79 sense-annotated verbs.

4 Annotation Process

In order to assure good quality of the manual sense annotation and to calculate inter-annotator agreement, sense annotation is independently performed by two annotators (native German computational linguists) for all word lemmas and occurrences. The annotators have the possibility to indicate problematic word occurrences with comments to be discussed separately.

The manual annotation is performed lemma-by-lemma (as in many related annotation projects, for example, [6], [11], [17], and [20]), i.e., an annotator first takes a look at all senses of a word in GermaNet and then – having in mind all possible senses – annotates each occurrence of that word in the TüBa-D/Z with the corresponding sense from GermaNet.

For each occurrence of a word in the treebank, the annotators are supposed to select exactly one GermaNet sense from the list of possible word senses, if possible. Since it is not always possible to select exactly one sense, i.e. it is either unclear or undecidable which of two senses is illustrated or none of the senses is plausible, the annotation guidelines allow the assignment of multiple senses or no sense for a word occurrence. The need to annotate more than one sense does not arise very often. This confirms both the results of [19] who annotated only 79 out of 2 421 occurrences with multiple senses, as well as the findings of [22, page 6] that “the average number of senses [...] is not very high, which shows that annotators have a tendency to avoid multiple answers.”

An experienced lexicographer, who is a native speaker of German and who has been the main responsible expert for the lexicographic extension of GermaNet for several years, supervises the two annotators. In an adjudication step, the experienced lexicographer goes through all occurrences, where the two annotators either do not agree or at least one of them had a comment, and resolves disagreements. This procedure of conducting independent annotations with an adjudication step afterwards is along the lines with most other sense-annotation projects, including for example [6], [12], and [17].

Where annotators found during the annotation process that a sense is missing from GermaNet, GermaNet is updated to include that sense. If the TüBa-D/Z contains occurrences of senses for the selected lemmas that are currently not covered by GermaNet, the two annotators indicate for these occurrences that a sense is missing in GermaNet. For example, the noun *Mann* had the following two senses in GermaNet 7.0: (i) ‘man’ in the general sense of an adult male person, and (ii) ‘husband’ in the more specific sense of a married man. In sentence (1), the noun *Mann* is used as a ‘unit for counting manpower’.

- (1) *Er will die Personalstärke der Bundeswehr auf 270.000 Mann reduzieren.*³
(‘He wants to reduce the manning level of the German Armed Forces to 270,000 men.’)

³Sentence 10 692 from TüBa-D/Z 9.

The lexicographic expert decides whether to add a missing sense to GermaNet. In the case of *Mann*, the mentioned *counting unit* sense has been included. The subsequent update of the sense inventory during the sense annotation process brings about mutual benefits both for the sense inventory which is being extended as well as for the sense-annotated corpus which profits from a feasible sense inventory. Such an update is common practice for all those annotation projects where the sense-annotated corpus is being created by the same research group which maintains the sense inventory (e.g., [11], [14], [15], and [17]).

5 Inter-Annotator Agreement

An inter-annotator agreement (IAA) score is calculated to assess the reliability of the manual sense annotations. The calculated percentage of IAA accounts for partial agreement using the Dice coefficient [22]. The overall percentage of agreement, which is obtained by averaging the Dice coefficient for all annotated occurrences of the word category in question, is 96.4% for nouns and 93.7% for verbs. This corresponds to Cohen's kappa \mathbf{K} [4] values of 85.4% and 82.4% for nouns and verbs, respectively.

The agreement for each of the 30 nouns is documented in columns *IAA* and \mathbf{K} in Table 3. With the two exceptions of *Höhe* (65.8%) and *Kette* (73.9%), the calculated IAA values for all other nouns are at least above 80%, mostly even above 90%. The explanation for the low agreement of the noun *Höhe* is due to the semantic distinction of the two word senses in GermaNet which are very fine-grained and turned out to be difficult to distinguish during the manual annotation process. The reason for a low performance for *Kette* stems from a subsequent restructuring of the sense inventory during the annotation process. A revision of senses in GermaNet has been performed after one annotator had already tagged 5 occurrences (which constitute already about 20%) with a sense of *Kette* that has been deleted. The tagging by the second annotator is conducted on the already revised set of senses and thus the deleted word sense is never chosen.

The kappa coefficients (column \mathbf{K} in Table 3) show a much higher deviation compared to the percentages of IAA. Here, the two by far worst results are obtained for *Höhe* (11.3) and *Bein* (-1.3), while all other kappa values lie above 60. The low \mathbf{K} for *Höhe* was to be expected as a result of an already low percentage of IAA. The explanation for a negative value for \mathbf{K} is that there is even less agreement between the annotators than an agreement by chance would be. The reason for the negative kappa value for *Bein* is due to the skewed distribution of annotated senses, i.e., the same predominant sense is assigned to all except one occurrence. The agreement by chance is thus nearly 1 and a deviation in the manual annotation influences the calculated coefficient enormously. For lemmas where both annotators always pick the same sense for all occurrences, Cohen's kappa is not informative. It is technically not possible to calculate the coefficient for these lemmas, because the agreement by chance is 1, which would result in a division

by zero. This is the reason why there are no \mathbf{K} values for the three nouns *Mal*, *Ausschuss*, and *Teilnahme*.

A detailed inspection of the IAA for single words did not show a correlation between the IAA and the polysemy of a noun. The Pearson correlation coefficient [18] between the IAA and the number of senses a noun has is -0.03, with a p -value of 0.88, i.e., without statistical significance. For example, the most problematic nouns mentioned above show different numbers of senses, i.e., 2 for *Höhe*, 3 for *Bein*, and 4 for *Kette*. Further, the reasons for the annotator disagreement are diverse and obviously not connected to the polysemy of a word, i.e., unclear sense distinction, skewed distribution of annotated senses, and subsequent update of the sense inventory, respectively. The other way around, the IAA values for the most polysemous nouns, i.e., 97.9% for *Land* (7 senses), 97.8% for *Kopf*, 92.0% for *Runde*, and 90.8% for *Bestimmung* (6 senses each) are comparable to the average of 96.4% for all annotated nouns. For nouns, this finding that there is no obvious correlation between the IAA and a word's polysemy corroborates the results reported by [6] on sense-annotating the Penn Treebank with senses from WordNet.

For each of the 79 verbs, the percentage of inter-annotator agreement (column IAA) and Cohen's kappa (column \mathbf{K}) are listed in Table 3. In general, the inter-annotator agreement for verbs is slightly lower than for nouns. However, similar to nouns, the calculated IAA values for most verbs are at least above 80%, mostly even above 90%. The few exceptions with a higher disagreement are *verschwinden* with 73.8%, *holen* with 74.2%, *kündigen* with 71.4%, *fressen* with 72.7%, and *wiedergeben* with 76.2%. For most of them (i.e., for *verschwinden*, *holen*, *kündigen*, and *wiedergeben*), the difficulty is mainly caused by a fine-grained distinction of senses which make an unambiguous annotation difficult. This detrimental effect for very fine-grained word senses was already observed by [16, page 97]. They report an improvement in the inter-annotator agreement from 71.3 to 82% for the same SensEval-2 lexical sample task when more coarse-grained verb senses are used instead of the fine-grained distinctions taken from WordNet 1.7. In the case of *holen*, an additional complexity arises due to the addition of two new word senses during the annotation process. For the verb *fressen*, most disagreements occur for transferred usages of the verb.

For the same reasons that cause a lower percentage of IAA, it was expected for those verbs to yield lower \mathbf{K} scores, which turned out to be true (i.e., *verschwinden* (47.4), *holen* (65.4), *kündigen* (42.9), *fressen* (54.3), and *wiedergeben* (40.0)). The explanation for kappa coefficients of 0.0 for the two verbs *existieren* and *vorschreiben* is a skewed distribution of annotated senses. Both for *existieren* and for *vorschreiben*, all except one occurrence (by one of the two annotators) are assigned the same word sense. This results in an agreement by chance of nearly 1 which in turn results in a very low kappa coefficient.⁴ For the verbs *betragen*,

⁴Since the chance agreements for these cases are nearly 1, Cohen's kappa is basically not informative for those cases, but since it is not exactly 1, it is technically possible to calculate the coefficient.

nützen, and *verlesen* no K values are given because both annotators always picked one sense for all occurrences and thus the coefficient is not informative for those lemmas.

For verbs, the observation for the TüBa-D/Z sense-annotation differs from [6]’s finding that there is no obvious correlation between the IAA and a word’s polysemy when sense-annotating the Penn Treebank. For the sense-annotation in the TüBa-D/Z, the Pearson correlation coefficient between the inter-annotator agreement and the polysemy of a verb is -0.39. The coefficient’s absolute value is not remarkably high⁵ to claim a strong correlation, but there is at least a higher correlation than for nouns, and, with a p -value smaller than 0.001, the correlation for verbs is statistically significant.

Overall, the reported percentage of IAA is very high. The values are comparable to the agreement statistics reported in [19] for their work in creating a German sense-annotated corpus. The observed agreement values are much higher than those observed for English. [22], for example, observes a pairwise Dice coefficient of 73% for nouns and 63% for verbs. [16] report an inter-annotator agreement of 71.3% for the English verb lexical sample task for SensEval-2. The reason for much higher IAA values for German than for English is the different number of distinct senses: an average of 4.1 for German nouns and 2.8 for German verbs as opposed to an average of 7.6 for English nouns and 12.6 for English nouns in the case of [22, Table 3].

6 Technical Integration into the Treebank

The TüBa-D/Z is released in different data formats, including NeGra export, export XML, Penn Treebank, TIGER-XML, and CoNLL. However, only three of the data formats in which the TüBa-D/Z is released are suitable to be extended with sense annotation. For each data format, the sense annotation refers to the sense in GermaNet 9.0, encoded by the ID of the corresponding lexical unit. In those cases, where no GermaNet sense can be annotated, the corresponding ID is set to -1. This occurs, for example, for idiomatic expressions or figurative meanings where it is not obvious from the context which sense to choose. For those annotations for which more than one GermaNet sense is selected, multiple lexical unit IDs are encoded. Such multiple IDs signal that either two senses are jointly represented by a specific word token or that it is undecidable which of two senses is represented by a specific word token.

The following subsections describe for each data format the appropriate extension needed for sense annotation. The newly added WSD information is underlined in the corresponding examples.

⁵Since ‘not remarkably high’ describes the absolute value of the correlation coefficient, it means that the coefficient is ‘not remarkably distinct from zero’.

NeGra export format

The line-oriented NeGra export format [1] represents each word token and each syntactic phrase node in a separate line. The following example shows an example line that encodes a word token:

```
sitzt sitzen VVFIN 3sis HD 503 %% LU=112247
```

The line encodes the word token itself (*sitzt*), followed by its lemma (*sitzen*), by its part-of-speech tag (*VVFIN*), its morphological tag (*3sis*), its phrasal edge label (*HD*), and its phrasal parent's node ID (*503*). In analogy to the annotation of referential relations in the TüBa-D/Z, sense annotations encoding the IDs of GermaNet lexical units are appended as comments to the corresponding lines representing the sense-annotated words in question (*%% LU=112247*).

Export XML format

This format represents all treebank information in a hierarchical XML structure. It encodes word tokens as separate XML elements. The following export XML example shows the same example as given above for the NeGra export format:

```
<word xml:id="s9_4" form="sitzt" pos="VVFIN" morph="3sis"
lemma="sitzen" func="HD" parent="s9_503" wsd-lexunits="112247"/>
```

The XML element `word` represents the word token in question with the XML attribute `form` for the token itself, the attribute `pos` for its part-of-speech tag, attribute `lemma` for its lemma, attribute `func` for its phrasal edge label, and attribute `parent` for the node ID of its phrasal parent. An `wsd-lexunits` XML attribute is added to the `word` element, which encodes the ID of the corresponding GermaNet lexical unit.

CoNLL 2012

The CoNLL format (in version 2012)⁶ also encodes each token in a separate line. It provides a separate column for word senses. The following example again represents the same token as before:

```
T990507.2 9 4 sitzt VVFIN ((LK:-(VXFIN:HD *))) sitzen 112247
```

The line first encodes a document ID (*T990507.2*), then the sentence number (*9*), followed by the word number within the sentence (*4*), followed by the word itself (*sitzt*), followed by its part-of-speech tag (*VVFIN*), followed by the corresponding parse bit (*((LK:-(VXFIN:HD *)))*), by the lemma (*sitzen*), and the word sense ID (*112247*).⁷

⁶<http://conll.cemantix.org/2012/data.html>

⁷Please note that the above example only displays a subset of all columns included in the canonical CoNLL 2012 format. Some columns, which encode information such as named entities, coreference, etc. and which are irrelevant for the example at hand, are omitted for reasons of space. Note

7 Related and Future Work

By integrating the sense annotations described in this paper into the most recent release of the TüBa-D/Z (release 9.1 as of December 2014), the sense annotations have been made available to the research community.⁸ In terms of quantity, the present study significantly goes beyond previous efforts on creating a German sense-annotated corpus in that 17 910 occurrences from the TüBa-D/Z treebank are annotated with the GermaNet senses of 30 nouns and 79 verbs.

Related studies which created sense-annotated corpora for German include [2, 10, 19, 23]. [2] annotated the GermaNet senses of 40 word lemmas (6 adjectives, 18 nouns, and 16 verbs) in 1 154 occurrences in the deWaC corpus. [19] annotated 2 421 occurrences of the EuroWordNet-GermaNet senses of 25 nouns in a medical corpus obtained from scientific abstracts from the Springer Link website. The same medical corpus was annotated by [23] with 24 ambiguous UMLS types – each of which occurs at least 11 times in the corpus (seven occur more than 100 times). [10] constructed the sense-annotated corpus WebCAGe semi-automatically by annotating more than 10 000 word occurrences in web-harvested texts with GermaNet senses of more than 2 000 word lemmas.

In future work, the sense annotations described in this paper will be used as a gold standard to evaluate German word sense disambiguation systems. The implementation of automatic disambiguation systems will employ the treebank’s grammatical information and investigate the impact of deep syntactic and semantic information for word sense disambiguation.

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References

- [1] Brants, Thorsten (1997) *The NeGra Export Format for Annotated Corpora (Version 3)*. Technical report, Computerlinguistik, Universität des Saarlandes, Germany.

also that the CoNLL 2012 format for the TüBa-D/Z data uses the column ‘lemma’ to specify the citation form of a word. This differs from the original CoNLL 2012 format where the column ‘lemma’ refers to predicates that have semantic role information.

⁸<http://www.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/en/ascl/resources/corpora/sense-annotated-tueba-dz.html>

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